

EFFECT OF HEATING CONDITIONS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MOLDED PRODUCT IN HYBRID MOLDING

Masaki Ohishi¹, Tadashi Uozumi², Akio Ohtani³, Asami Nakai⁴

¹Advanced Fibro-Science, Kyoto Institute of Technology
Matsugasaki, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8585 JAPAN
Email: m.ohishi@satoh-gr.co.jp, web page: <http://www.kit.ac.jp>

²Gifu University Composite Materials Center
1-1 Yanagido, Gifu City 501-1193, JAPAN
Email: uozumi@gifu-u.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.gifu-u.ac.jp>

³Gifu University Composite Materials Center
1-1 Yanagido, Gifu City 501-1193, JAPAN
Email: a_ohtani@gifu-u.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.gifu-u.ac.jp>

⁴Department of Mechanical Engineering Faculty of Engineering, Gifu University
1-1 Yanagido, Gifu City 501-1193, JAPAN
Email: nakai@gifu-u.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.gifu-u.ac.jp>

Keywords: GF RTP, CFR TP, Hybrid molding, Thermoplastic

ABSTRACT

The adoption of fiber reinforced plastic attracts attention from the industry, as a strong candidate for weight reduction method. Hybrid molding is one of the manufacturing methods using the fiber reinforced thermoplastic resin composite as a prepreg substrate. Hybrid molding is the combined molding process of compression and injection molding for fiber reinforced thermo plastics, therefore composite structural materials with the mounting members and the rib of parts can be fabricated at one time by using the process. Knowing the effects on the mechanical properties of change of the molding conditions in this molding is essential in order to improve the quality of the molded article. In this study, the molded product with a rib structure was obtained by hybrid molding that changed preheated conditions and injection resin temperature with reinforced thermo-plastic composite. The strength of the rib parts of injection resin and interfacial properties between woven composites and injected parts were examined by tensile test with T-shaped specimens which were taken out of it. The strength of the rib was decreased at the high temperature area of prepreg preheating and injection resin. The interfacial bonding strength was decreased by heating the prepreg at higher particular temperature. Fracture aspect was changed by heating conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

As global environmental conservation grows more important around the world, automobile makers are working to make cars lighter to reduce CO₂ emissions and fuel using. Composite materials such as carbon fiber reinforced plastics in order to lightweight have been adopted in automotive parts. Hybrid molding method is one of the molding methods of Fiber Reinforced Thermo Plastics (FRTP). The method of combination injection molding and press forming is attracted attention, while there are several methods of FRTP hybrid molding. In such the hybrid molding, a method of "Pre-heated continuous fiber prepreg and the short fiber-containing molten resin supplied by an injection device are molded in the same mold at same time" is representative. This method for integrate the resin and prepreg in one process, there is the advantage that after process such as hole drilling, trimming of outer circumference and bonding are unnecessary. In the molding of the FRTP, various factors such as heating method and transfer method of prepreg, mold temperature and molding conditions has been found to effect of mechanical properties of the molded article. Therefore, optimization and the

understanding of the molding condition are essential for the quality improvement of the molding parts in hybrid molding. However, there are no previous studies on effect of molding condition on strength of the article and the bond strength of prepreg and injection resin. In this study, the molded articles with a rib structure were hybrid molded on in different prepreg preheat and injection resin temperature. The tensile strength and interface strength of rib parts was measured using the T-shaped specimen obtained from it, and temperature dependence of their strength was investigated.

2 EXPLANATION OF HYBRID MOLDING

Figure 1 is a process of the hybrid molding method. The prepreg of containing continuation fibers are transferred to the heating unit. It is then transferred into the press unit and placed on the mold after being heated for a predetermined time. Then, softening the continuous fiber prepreg material is shaped by press unit, and same time supplies the molten thermoplastic resin by injection unit to form an additional form of ribs or the like in a thermoplastic resin. The hybrid molding is completed in this series of steps, prepreg and injection resin material is integrated in the same process.

Figure 1: Process of the hybrid molding method.

3 EXPERIMENT METHODS

3.1 Materials

The Prepreg material Tepex-dynalite 102 of continuous glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic material manufactured BOND-LAMINATE were used. This material is composed of laminated continuous glass reinforcing fibers of PA6 nylon resin and fibers volume is 45 vol. %. There are plate shapes and various thickness sizes, in this time it 460x320mm size and 1.5mm thickness was used. The Injection resin material was used DURETHAN BKV30 H2.0 manufactured by LANXESS. The matrix resin of this material is PA6 nylon containing intermittently 16 vol. % glass fibers.

3.2 Molding condition and equipments

The molding was used a hybrid molding machine VIM1003 manufactured SATOH MACHINERY. This device have vertical press unit of the clamping force 980kN and horizontal injection unit of the injection volume 300cc. The preheating of prepreg was used a far infrared rays heating furnace. After preheating was complete, it was set on the mold in the press unit by hand using jig.

Table 1 shows the molding conditions. Constant molding conditions were press pressure 10 MPa and mold temperature by controller unit set to 95 °C. Altered molding conditions were molten resin temperature and preheating temperature of prepreg. The temperature of a molten resin was changed by setting temperature of the injection unit heater. Preheating of the prepreg by far infrared rays heating furnace it was confirmed in preliminary experiments that setting temperature of the heating

furnace to a predetermined temperature is obtained in the heating time of 4 minutes.

Press presser [MPa]	Injection resin temperature [°C]	Prepreg preheating temperature [°C]	Mold temperature [°C]
10	270	265	95
10	270	270	95
10	270	280	95
10	270	290	95
10	270	300	95
10	270	310	95
10	270	320	95
10	290	290	95
10	290	310	95
10	290	330	95

Table 1: Molding conditions

3.3 Tensile test

The shape of molding parts is shown in figure 2. This article is a box shaped with the rib on the inside. The rib is composed of resin supplied by injection unit. Opposite side of rib is a molding parts surface was placement prepreg. The paint parts of the molding article in the figure were cut to have a T-shaped test piece. Tensile tests were conducted, after setting it in the jig of shown in figure. The tensile properties were measured using a universal testing machine (ORIENTEC) at a constant speed of 0.5 mm/min.

Figure 2: Molding parts and test piece.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results of tensile test

Figure 3 of the square markers and solid line shows relationship between tensile strength obtained in tensile tests and prepreg preheating temperature. Constant strength was observed at less than preheats temperature 310 °C. The strength over 310 °C of preheats temperature were decreases gradually. Figure 4 of the circle markers and solid line shows relationship between tensile strength and injection resin temperature. The strength was decreased in the upper range of 310 °C, whereas the strength was constant between injection resin temperatures 270 °C to 310 °C.

Figure 3: Relationship between tensile strength and prepreg preheating temperature.

Figure 4: Relationship between tensile strength and injection resin temperature.

Figure 5 shows fracture state after tensile test of test pieces. White part of the figure is constituted by resin was supplied by the injection unit and paint part shows prepreg. Both materials were bonded after molding. The fracture state had two types, one of the type was broken only the injected resin part without interfacial debonding (Type I). Other one type was fractured with interfacial debonding between injection resin and prepreg (Type II). The fracture states of Type II were seen many in over 310 °C area of prepreg preheat temperature in which the tensile strength was decreased. The fracture states under 310 °C range of prepreg preheat temperature and molding of changing the injection resin temperature had Type I state.

Figure 5: Fracture state types.

4.2 Bonding strength of the interface section

Since the mechanical properties of rib parts were found to effect the prepreg preheat and injection resin temperature change, moreover the destruction with interfacial debonding was seen at high temperature heating of prepreg. Therefore the temperature dependence of the bonding strength of the

interface section was investigated. The resin part of test piece at rib base were made notch by cutter as shown in schematic diagram in figure 3 and figure 4. Then it was subjected to the tensile test after attaching test jig. Figure 3 of the triangle markers and dotted line shows relationship between bonding strength and prepreg preheating temperature. Similar to the test without notch, the strength was decreased over 310 °C. In contrast, there was decrease in the strength under 300 °C. Figure 4 of the diamonds markers and dotted line shows relationship between bonding strength and injection resin temperature. The strength was over 310 °C area shows low values in same trend as the circle markers, however less than 310 °C of it showed constant. In the case of prepreg preheating temperature is low; the injection resin was cooled faster as compared with high temperature preheating. This temperature drop is considered to affect the reduction in interfacial strength. The resin contained in prepreg was caused to thermal degradation by excessive heating at high temperature prepreg preheating. This was believed to cause of the decrease in interface strength at high temperature area.

4.3 Structural analysis

In figure 3, the bounding strength was reduced under 300 °C, but tensile strength was constant. When measuring the thickness of the test pieces, they were different in prepreg preheating temperature. Figure 6 shows thickness of molded parts flat surface at each temperature. The thickness is decreased with increasing temperature. Since the thickness of the prepreg dosed not change by temperature, a thickness change part was configuring injection resin parts. When the prepreg temperature was low, the injection resin temperature was reduced as a result was a flow of the injection resin got worse. It is believed that thicknesses of the molded parts were increased. Similarly, the thickness relationship between the injected resin temperatures was investigated and it result was shown in figure 7. The thickness was decreased linearly with increasing the resin temperature. When the resin temperature increases better the fluidity of the resin, as a result it is believed the thickness of the molded article was thinned.

Figure 6: Relationship between molded parts thickness and prepreg preheating temperature.

Figure 7: Relationship between molded parts thickness and injection resin temperature.

Since the change in thickness of the molded product due to the temperature conditions were observed, the relationship between the thickness and the tensile strength were researched. It shows the results in Figure 8. The circle markers and solid line shows case of prepreg preheat temperature change and the triangle markers and dotted line shows condition that changed injection resin temperature. The strength was increased as the thickness of the molded parts becomes thicker in both cases. Especially the strength of preheat temperature change had greatly affected by thickness. The difference in molding temperature is varying the thickness of the molded parts, and it was by changing the strength.

Figure 8: Relationship between molded parts thickness and tensile strength.

Therefore, effects of the change in thickness of the resin on mechanical properties were examined by structural analysis. Figure 9 shows the conditions and results of FEM structural analysis. The thickness of the rib was in constant at 3mm and the load of breakdown strength of each thickness was added in vertically rib upper side. It was constrained the back surface of test piece similarly to the case in jig setting, as shown in pink line. In the calculation was used modulus of elasticity 2.62GPa and Poisson's ratio 0.34 at injection resin part and modulus of elasticity 10.0GPa and Poisson's ratio 0.4 at prepreg part. As an example, it was shown in figure the structural analysis results of the thickness at 2.0mm and 2.5mm. It had wide high stress range of rib base parts (circle A) 2.5mm than 2.0mm. Focusing on the portion corresponding to the interface was shown circle B parts in figure, differences due to the thickness it was not seen.

Figure 9: FEM structural analysis.

Figure 10 shows relationship between the stress that obtained by analysis and thickness. The square markers show the stress of rib base at part A and the triangle markers show the stress of interface parts between resin supplied by injection and prepreg at part B. The stress at rib base was increased to the thickness of the molded product becomes thick, in contrast, there was no much change in the stress of the interface section. The cause of destruction with the interfacial debonding more than 310 °C preheating temperature was lowering bonding strength by the resin thermal degradation at the interface was added by thin resin parts. The difference in the strength was not observed below 310 °C preheating temperature, since the difference of the molded product thickness due to the change in

temperature was small. It is believed to have become fracture state of interfacial debonding when resin thickness is thin, since the high stress applied to the A portion approaches the surface. Though the thickness of the article was thicker, the strength decreases in the vicinity of injection resin temperature 270 °C was shown in figure 4. The destruction at this temperature was destruction in the resin part; an ejection resin has the cause of the strength drop. It is believed that the fiber orientation and the flow of the ejection resin are influenced by resin temperature. Their mechanism does not become clear.

Further study is needed to understand the mechanisms of injection resin parts.

Figure 10: Relationship between stress and thickness

5 CONCLUSION

The mechanical properties was lowered at high prepreg preheat temperature, the fracture state was changed to destruction with interfacial debonding from destruction of the resin part supplied by injection unit. The fracture state was resin part destruction when the injection resin temperature was changed. The strength was different with resin temperature. It was also confirmed by the dependence of resin temperature. The bonding strength of the interface between prepreg and resin also had temperature dependence. The condition of molding was found to setting temperature with better bonding strength. Further the thickness of the resin part was changed the stress of rib base however, there was no effect on the strength of the interface. The resin flow and fiber orientation were presumed to affect the strength in the injection molded at a low resin temperature range however, it mechanism was unclear. That is the study from now on.